

Speculation on the Interplay of X and Time in Quantum Bound States

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 28, 2023

In Newtonian mechanics, one often thinks in terms of $x(t)$ i.e. an association between x and t . Although this is part of Newtonian mechanics, the notion of motion always being linked to time (and so an internal clock being required) is not always the case. For example, two particles with different masses and different velocities such that their momenta are the same may strike a target and reflect with the same magnitude of momenta. The impulse is $2p$ for both even though they have different speeds. One does not need to consider their speed to discuss the impulse change and so an external clock is not needed.

This is further emphasized by the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ which separates x and t as if they were independent variables (even though implicitly a speed exists in the problem i.e. $v = dx/dt$). The point is that there exists a subset of physics (i.e. interactions) which is not dependent on velocity and hence the presence of a clock. The impulse hit discussed above is one example, but interference through 2 slits etc is another. Two quantum particles with the same momentum, but different rest masses and velocities produce the same interference patterns.

A particle with momentum, however, has energy and so both time and space are running variables, but there are problems in which one considers p without a clock. Interestingly, even if one thinks in terms of impulses without using a clock, if there is an x interval between impulses then the notion of velocity comes into play even without an external clock because there will be more impulses imparted by a fixed p with a higher velocity than a lower one in the same fixed time period. Without using the idea of a clock, this gives rise to the observable called pressure in classical physics, but is also present in a quantum bound state, we argue. Pressure in classical physics is proportional to temperature which in turn is proportional to energy (and a running time). In a quantum bound state, the equivalent to pressure (namely impulse hits with a potential) also require an energy viewpoint which is linked to running time i.e. $\exp(-i E_n t)$ where E_n is the bound energy.

Is an External Clock Always Required?

Newtonian mechanics is often thought of in terms of $x(t)$ i.e. this is the sought-after solution of Newton's second law which is equivalent to a Lagrangian differential equation. This gives the sense that both an external ruler and external clock are needed. This is not, however, always the case in Newtonian mechanics. Two particles with the same momentum, but different rest masses and velocities may hit a screen and bounce back with the same magnitude of momentum. The impulse is $2p$ and no external ruler or clock is needed to describe this situation.

In (1) we argued that for a particle at rest (with rest mass equal to energy), there should still be a sense of time even if an external clock is removed. We thus argued that energy needs to be associated with periodicity in time because this is needed to create the sense of a clock. We used $A = -Et + px$ with $x=0$ and considered the eigenvalue equation:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt) \quad ((1))$$

We then argued that $A = -Et + px$ separates time and x and so if E represents an internal clock, p should represent an internal ruler with periodicity yielding ruler gradations i.e.:

$$-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((2)) \quad (\text{constant momentum } p)$$

Even though p is associated with a $v = dx/dt$ which in turn depends on an external ruler and clock, p itself is a physical observable through impulse hits which do not require a clock or ruler to measure. Thus there may be physical interactions, such as bouncing off a wall, or even two slit interference etc which do not require the presence of an external ruler or clock.

One may immediately note, however, that a constant momentum necessarily means an energy and this in turn implies a running time. Furthermore, v is implicitly part of the definition of both constant momentum and its corresponding energy. Velocity dx/dt deals with travel over x in t . If an impulse hit does not depend on velocity, how does velocity manifest itself?

We argue that this occurs through the notion of pressure, but pressure requires localized motion i.e. motion to the right and left after hitting boundary walls. Thus, two classical particles with the same momentum p , but different rest masses and velocities, will impart the same impulse to one wall and then to the other. The faster moving particle, however, hits the two walls which represent boundaries more often and so creates the sense of more impulses in a fixed amount of time i.e. higher pressure. How is this linked to energy (in a nonrelativistic sense)?

Consider a particle with m, v and another with $.5m, 2v$. The latter hits the walls twice as many times in a given time period. Now put two m, v particles and one $.5m, 2v$ particles into two different boxes. In terms of impulses which do not consider time or a clock, the pressure is the same in the two boxes. If one considers nonrelativistic Newtonian mechanics, then the energies are:

$$\text{Box 1: } .5 (.5m) 2v 2v = mv^2 \quad \text{Box 2 } 2 (.5 mv^2) = mv^2 \quad ((3))$$

Thus the two boxes with the same pressure also have the same energy. This is identical to the ideal gas law:

$$PV = nRT \quad \text{where } T = \text{temperature which is proportional to energy} \quad ((4))$$

Thus even though impulses by themselves do not require a clock, impulses occurring in a bound (localized) system are affected by velocity which in turn gives rise to the notion of pressure which is linked to energy. Energy is then linked to running time in quantum mechanics. We apply this argument to the single particle quantum bound state.

Quantum Bound State

A quantum free particle is described by the wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. This does not depend directly on v and so does not require an external clock i.e. $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$. What happens if one places such a particle in a potential $V(x)$?

In Newtonian mechanics, one would have acceleration i.e. $dv/dt = dv/dx \cdot dx/dt$ within a fixed dx . {Aside: $\exp(ipx)$, however, is associated with a wavelength \hbar/p which may be larger than $dx \rightarrow 0$. Thus the idea of $dv/dx \cdot dx/dt$ is problematic in quantum mechanics.} Consider two classical particles with the same p , but different masses and velocities. Newton's second law states:

$$dp/dt = F(x) \text{ with } F(x) \text{ acting in a fixed } dx \rightarrow dv/dx \cdot p = F(x) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) shows that the two particles have the same change dv for a fixed dx , and so undergo different dp changes. Thus even though they have the same momentum, the constraint of a fixed dx means that motion within $F(x)$ is ultimately linked to an external clock i.e. energy because the result ((5)) is velocity dependent. Newton's second law applies to motion in one direction, but one may always create a bound system by adding walls. Thus ((5)) may also be considered a result pertaining to a bound classical particle. In such a case, $E = p^2/2m + V(x)$ is constant at each x so one considers energy and an external clock.

A quantum free particle, however, is represented by $\exp(ipx)$, where p is a constant, which does not change from one dx to another. If $F(x) = -dV/dx$ is present, then what occurs? One may argue that p implies impulse hits which do not require an external clock. $V(x)$, may be written in terms of impulses as well i.e.

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((6))$$

Why is $V(x)$ used instead of $F(x)$ (force)? $A = -Et + px$ for constant E, p shows that E and p are the variables of a special relativistic 4-vector, so we wish to consider these. If impulse hits occur between the quantum particle and $V(x)$ (written as ((6))) and impulse hits do not require a clock, why should energy be of any concern? Energy is associated with a running time, but one considers this a time-independent (equilibrium type of problem) {Aside: hence the expression "time-independent Schrodinger equation".}

We argue that just as in the case of a particle in box (i.e. pressure), a single quantum bound particle undergoes impulse hits which do not require an external clock. If the particle, however, has a particular p and a rest mass m_1 , it has a velocity v_1 . We argue that a fast velocity should lead to more or at least different interactions with $V(x)$ than a slow one even though p is the same. Thus even though m_1 and m_2 may have the same p as free particles (with different v 's v_1 and v_2), interactions with $V(x)$ yield a different pressure profile (just as in the case of two particles with the same p within a box). In the quantum case, one cannot change the particle number, there is a single particle. It does seem, however, that for different rest masses, there should be different bound energies and so one needs to think of this problem in terms of energy. Thus one may write:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

where $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to p (impulse) and does not need an external clock, but the $a(p)$ may be linked explicitly to energy. Thus one creates an average conservation of energy equation. (This

equation would have been expected because one uses $V(x)$, but the interactions of $V(x)$ and $\exp(ipx)$'s are different than the Newtonian picture.) Thus we suggest:

$$\left\{ \sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad (8)$$

In other words, even though impulse hits don't require a clock, when a particle is localized, the notion of velocity becomes important and velocity does require an external clock for its measurement. Time is linked to energy and so one requires an energy equation. Thus one has a hybrid of impulses, which do not require a clock, with weights which are linked to a picture in which velocity and hence energy determine their value and are associated with a clock. Thus the root mean square momentum may be described classically as moving through time like a classical particle, even though one may knock out a quantum particle in a state $\exp(ipx)$ which is linked with an impulse and may undergo 2-slit interference etc with no external clock required.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ separates t and x which seems to be at odds with the Newtonian notion of $x(t)$ which requires an external clock. In Newtonian mechanics, however, there exists the notion of impulse which does not require an external clock. For example, $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ with $v_2 > v_1$. One does not need to know about v_1 or v_2 , the impulse hits of both are the same. Thus there exists some physics (interactions) which do not require an external clock. An impulse hit is one example, but $\exp(ipx)$ interactions with 2 slits etc are another.

In a classical gas, one also has impulse hits, but given the bound nature of the problem (localized length), flux becomes important and pressure requires the notion of velocity i.e. an external clock. For example, $2pv_1$ and $2pv_2$ are the pressures of two particles with the same p and different velocities. Pressure may be physically measured without a clock and is proportional to temperature (measured by a thermometer) which in turn is proportional to energy (and hence a running time we argue). Thus even in an impulse picture, localization ensures that velocity and hence energy is important. We apply these ideas to a quantum bound particle.

A quantum free particle is represented by $\exp(ipx)$ which does not explicitly show velocity and so does not require an external clock. Imagine that $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ i.e. that impulse hits occur between a fixed p and k . This leads to an ensemble: $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. If impulse hits occur, why should a clock (i.e. energy) come into the picture? We argue that even though $\exp(ipx) \exp(ikx)$ does not depend on the velocity associated with p (i.e. rest mass), different rest masses give rise to different velocities and to a different pressure profile even in the quantum system. Pressure is linked with energy, thus we argue that even using $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ representing impulse hits, one needs an energy equation to determine $a(p)$ hence: $\left\{ \sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n$. Particles with different m values have different numerical solutions. Thus time ultimately appears in this problem as manifested by $\exp(-iE_n t)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Energy, Momentum and Running Time and Space X Variables?
(preprint, zenodo, 2023)